

Evaluation of Staphylococcal superantigen-like 7 from *Staphylococcus aureus* for human serum IgA purification

Milan Prodanović¹, Nemanja Mijin¹, Sara Krstić, David Mardokić, Milan Kojić¹, Ivana Prodić¹, Rajna Minić^{1*}

¹The Institute of Virology, Vaccines and Sera "Torlak"

Immunoglobulin A (IgA) is a crucial antibody class at mucosal surfaces. In serum it remains underexplored. This study focuses on developing an in house method for the purification of serum IgA using the Staphylococcal superantigen-like 7 (SSL7) protein derived from *Staphylococcus aureus*. Previous findings suggest our clinical isolate of *S. aureus* binds human IgA, potentially due to the surface presence of SSL7. To utilise this fact for IgA purification the SSL7 gene was PCR amplified and cloned into pQE-Ek expression vector. The sequence identity was confirmed by Sanger sequencing. Computed protein parameters were Mw 25170,3 Da and pI 8.74. High levels of soluble His-tagged SSL7 protein were expressed and purified using metal-affinity chromatography from the bacterial cell lysate. Purified 25 kDa protein was immobilized on a commercial Sepharose matrix. Application of this matrix demonstrated specific binding, evidenced by protein bands corresponding to immunoglobulin heavy and light chains, alongside a minor fraction (9,7%) of non-corresponding proteins. Western blot analysis confirmed preference for IgA binding over the binding of IgG and IgM. This study demonstrates the potential of using SSL7 from *S. aureus* as an affinity ligand for the selective purification of IgA from human serum, but to obtain IgA of higher purity this step should be followed by protein G affinity purification. Given the known affinity of SSL7 for both human IgA and complement component C5, future modifications will include site-specific mutagenesis to abolish C5 interaction, and examination of the effects of this mutation on binding different antibody classes.

*Corresponding Author:

Rajna Minić, Principal Research Fellow

Head of the Protein Engineering and Biochemistry department, Research and Science division, Institute of Virology, Vaccines, and Sera "Torlak", 458, Vojvode Stepe, 11152 Belgrade, Serbia, rminic@torlak.rs

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